

Appendix 1

Rapid drug desensitisation: One-bag protocol for intravenously administered biologics

This infusion plan applies to biologics dissolved in 525 ml. Infusion sets are primed with drug solution.

(According to regulations, infusion bags of 500 ml solvent (saline or glucose) should contain at least 500 ml, but in reality most contain up to 525 ml)

Following parameters of 11 infusion steps are coded in high precision infusion pumps (Infusomat Space® Braun)

Infusion steps	Volume to infuse (ml)	Duration (min)	Infusion rate (ml/h)	Percentage of a standard infusion rate† (%)	Percentage of target dose each step (%)	Cumulative percentage of target dose (%)
Step 1	0.7	15	2.8	0.5	0.1	0.1
Step 2	1.3	15	5.2	1	0.2	0.4
Step 3	2.6	15	10.4	2	0.5	0.9
Step 4	5.3	15	21.2	4	1.0	1.9
Step 5	10.5	15	42.0	8	2.0	3.9
Step 6	15.8	15	63.2	12	3.0	6.9
Step 7	21.0	15	84.0	16	4.0	10.9
Step 8	52.5	30	105.0	20	10.0	20.9
Step 9	57.8	30	115.6	22	11.0	31.9
Step 10	63.0	30	126.0	24	12.0	43.9
Step 11	294.7	135	131.0	25	56.1	100
Final flushing	When the infusion bag with drug solvent is emptied, the infusion set still contains drug solvent. A infusion bag containing only flushing fluid is connected to the infusion set and infusion step 11 should be completed (all 135 min.), before increasing the infusion rate to 300 ml/h for 10 min.					
Total infusion time	5 hours and 40 minutes, including final flushing					

† A standard infusion rate is 525 ml/h, corresponding to a standard infusion duration of 1 hour.

Rapid drug desensitisation protocol for etanercept**Target dose 50 mg**

Medicine used

Etanercept 25mg, vials with powder and solvent for injection fluid, (e.g. Enbrel®) .

Reconstructed solutions for injection

Etanercept (Enbrel®) is reconstituted with 1 ml water for injections (sterile water). Chemical and physical stability has been demonstrated for 6 hours after reconstitution at temperatures up to 25°C.

Additional solutions for RDD

Three vials are used: vial A, B and C.

The concentration of reconstructed solution for injection is 25 mg/ml

Dilution α

From vial A, take 0.3 ml (etanercept 25 mg/ml) and add to a sterile vial.

Add 1.2 ml of sterile NaCl to the same vial.

Total volume: 1.5 ml

Concentration: 5 mg/ml

Overall plan for RDD

Seven doses are given at 30 min. intervals.

Steps 1-3 are given from dilution α .

Step 4-7 are given undiluted vials A, B and C

Steps	Dilution	Volumes (ml)	doses	Notes
1	Dilution α	0,1	0,5 mg	
2	Dilution α	0,2	1 mg	
3	Dilution α	0,4	2 mg	Discard the rest of solution α
4	Undiluted, Vial A	0,2	5 mg	Discard the rest of vial A
5	Undiluted, Vial B	0,4	10 mg	
6	Undiluted, Vial B	0,6	15 mg	Corresponding to rest of vial B
7	Undiluted, Vial C	0,66	16,5 mg	Discard the rest of vial C

Observation: 2 hours after last dose.

Subsequent treatment: Injections twice a week with etanercept 25 mg for minimum two weeks. Once tolerated without significant injection site reactions, the patient can proceed weekly injections of etanercept 50 mg.
